

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

COP29: AZERBAIJANI MODEL IN THE FIGHT AGAINST CLIMATE CHANGE

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Abstract

The study examines issues related to environmental pollution and climate change. In modern conditions, the “green” economy is quite important for countries' successful economic and environmental development. This paper shows how Azerbaijan uses the principles of a “green” economy to develop its economic system and also protects the environment within the country. In addition, the article emphasizes the prospects for the development of this area in the liberated territories of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: Azerbaijan, President, Karabakh, liberated lands, green world, climate change, smart city, smart village.

*The energy potential of Azerbaijan can become
an effective stimulus for economic growth world-
wide!*

Heydar Aliyev

As we know, the anthropogenic and technogenic impact of humans on the environment, due to the global growth of industrial production and energy consumption, has brought humanity to the brink of an environmental disaster on a global scale. Emissions of pollutants into the atmosphere, oil spills, and sewage pollution lead not only to the extinction of certain species of flora and fauna and climate change on the planet but also to an increase in population mortality and the progression of fatal diseases. In this regard, for the preservation and development of humanity, it is vital to make a transition to a new development paradigm and reduce pressure on the environment through the introduction of environmentally friendly technologies that will not expose future generations to significant environmental risks. For example, over time, moving away from internal combustion engines and coal-fired power plants will lead to a healthier environment. Some European countries such as Denmark, Great Britain and France are planning to close the centers to gasoline and diesel cars over the coming decades.

Today, for the reasons stated above, global climate change and the transition to green energy are hot topics that attract everyone's attention. The term “green” economy was first coined by British economists David Pearce, Anil Markandya and Edward Barbier in a report to the UK Government in 1989 entitled “Blueprint for a Green Economy” and global interest in green economy has grown significantly since the term was first mentioned. The main idea behind the green economy comes from David Pearce, a leading resource and environmental economist. It was the science of resources and the environment that was the founder of the development of the concept of a “green” economy. The concept of a “green” economy, as the basis of development policy, laid down in the works of British scientists, is currently widely reflected in the scientific research discourse, gaining ground in various research areas that

focus on the political, economic and social aspects of this phenomenon. It is the energy sector that is considered one of the most important in the formation of a new economic model, taking into account the fact that the energy sector is the largest source of carbon dioxide emissions. It is recognized that the main role in the fight against climate change and its negative consequences should be played by industrialized countries with economies in transition. “Responsible for the majority of greenhouse gas emissions, they [developed countries] must not only come up with innovative solutions for the energy transition, but also implement them,” said UK renewable energy expert Nick Medich [10, web].

On December 25, 2023, President Ilham Aliyev, guided by paragraph 32 of Article 109 of the Constitution of the Republic of Azerbaijan, to strengthen international solidarity in the global fight against climate change, signed the Order “On declaring 2024 in the Republic of Azerbaijan the “Year of Solidarity for the Green World.” It should be brought to your attention that the logical consequence of the government’s work to contribute to the fight against climate change, the transition to a green economy and the undeniable authority of Azerbaijan in the international arena was the adoption of a decision at the COP28 conference in Dubai (2023) to hold in November 2024 in Baku one of the largest and most prestigious events in the world - the 29th session of the Conference of the Parties to the UN Framework Convention on Climate Change COP29. Holding this conference will provide an opportunity to demonstrate to the world the achievements of our country in the matter of technological solutions in the field of energy transition. In 2023, during the working visit of President Ilham Aliyev to Abu Dhabi, the United Arab Emirates, an agreement was signed between the State Oil Company of the Azerbaijan Republic (SOCAR) and the local company Masdar on the joint development of offshore wind and hydrogen projects with a capacity of 2 GW, and an agreement to jointly develop 1 GW of solar photovoltaic and 1 GW of onshore wind projects” [5, web].

It is important to state that Azerbaijan, a country with enormous potential for renewable energy sources

(RES), is an example of a successful transition to alternative energy sources and, as a reliable, responsible member of the international community, makes a tangible contribution to the fight against the consequences of climate change. From this position, "Azerbaijan has set a goal to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by 35 percent by 2030 compared to the base year of 1990, and by 40 percent by 2050. Azerbaijan aims to increase the share of renewable energy sources in installed electricity production capacity to 30 percent by 2030" [6, web]. Our state also plans to implement a SOCAR project to lay electrical cables to offshore platforms in the country to reduce consumption at natural gas facilities, as well as a program to build an underwater cable along the bottom of the Black Sea to transport green energy from Azerbaijan to Europe. Creating types and transporting green energy to world markets is certainly a priority of Azerbaijan's energy policy. In the field of alternative energy, the Azerbaijani government plans to implement a project to build a power plant in Yashma and transform Nakhichevan into a green energy zone along with Karabakh and Eastern Zangezur. "The possibility of constructing a solar power plant with a capacity of 500 MW is being considered; launch a solar power plant with a capacity of 240 MW in Jebrazil, the direct foreign investor of which is the British company BP (British Petroleum)" [7, web].

It should be noted that according to official documents, the five National Priorities for the socio-economic development of Azerbaijan, which must be implemented before 2030, are the following: a steadily developing competitive economy; a vibrant, inclusive and socially just society; competitive human capital and the space of modern innovations; the Great Return to the territories liberated from occupation; a clean environment and a green growth country. Due to the fact that digital sectors are the fastest growing, the current national strategy of Azerbaijan "Strategies for the socio-economic development of the Republic of Azerbaijan for 2022-2026", approved by President Ilham Aliyev, most of all focuses on digital technologies. The future economic development of Azerbaijan will be closely linked to the use of environmentally friendly technologies, clean energy sources, waste recycling and measures to rehabilitate contaminated areas. Azerbaijan is building smart cities/villages on ancestral lands liberated from the Armenian occupation. It should be indicated that after the great victory in the Patriotic War, Azerbaijan faces the most important task of restoring Karabakh. President Ilham Aliyev noted in one of his speeches that the liberated lands should be restored using the concept of "smart city" and "smart village". The liberated lands should be areas of high-tech development. First of all, it is necessary to prepare the primary digital infrastructure, to create a base that will allow developing the liberated lands precisely in the direction of high technologies. The favorable geographical location of the country and natural resources, human potential, as well as the state programs, decrees and orders adopted in recent years by the President, create all the opportunities for it.

It is also worth noting another important point that the main concepts for urban planning provided for in

the State Program for the Great Return to the Liberated Lands are "Smart City", "Smart Village" and "The green energy zone". Let us recall that in May 2021, President Ilham Aliyev signed a decree on measures to create a "Green Energy" zone in the territory of Azerbaijan liberated from occupation. Sometimes the question arises: why does a "smart" city need "green" energy? Deloitte analysts claim that the idea of a "smart" city is inextricably linked with "green" energy since it helps create a favorable environment for residents.

"Green" energy is part of an energy-producing system that does not pollute the environment and is renewable. The most common types of green energy are photovoltaic conversion of solar energy, wind, rain, tides, etc. This is because they are easily available on Earth and can be replenished naturally. According to an academician Zh. Alferova, "The conversion of solar energy into electrical energy is our future. The sun is an inexhaustible source of energy, our thermonuclear reactor, which has been operating steadily for billions of years" [8, web]. "Smart cities are able to offer people an alternative, better and safer reality, which means that they are needed - and urgently - not only for a more complete physical and intellectual self-realization of a person but also for maintaining the viability of our planet" [2, p. 445]. The concept of a smart city/village is based on the use of modern information technologies and communications to comprehensively improve the levels of health protection, security, education and employment of the population, to create additional opportunities for recreation and sustainable well-being of citizens. A smart city/village simplifies the management of internal urban processes and makes the life of residents more comfortable and safer.

In this regard, within the framework of the concept of "Smart City" and "Smart Village", the construction of houses has already been completed in the village of Agaly (Agaly-1, Agaly-2, Agaly-3) of the Zangelan district. Of course, "Smart Village" in Agali is already one of the central settlements of the East Zangezur region since it is the first among other villages to act as a locomotive in "smart" construction in the liberated territories. The village, once consisting of ruins, is now a clean, built-up, ennobled area in which life is in full swing. Therefore, the "Smart Village" in the village of Agali can be considered as an Azerbaijani model. In addition, construction work is being carried out in the Kelbajar, Jabrail, and Gubadli regions as well as in the village of Dovletyarly in the Fizuli region. In Azerbaijan, regarding "Smart City" and "Smart Village", the concept of Singapore and Dubai has been put forward. A feature of this concept is the electronization of the entire infrastructure, in particular transport, educational and medical institutions, power plants, water supply systems and other public facilities, to create a large information base, etc. According to the project, green and alternative energy will be used, as well as "Smart management", "Smart agriculture". The concepts of "smart city", "smart village" and "green energy" imply the use of "smart" solutions. These could be solutions such as "smart" street lighting, "smart" management of household waste, the construction of hydroelectric power stations and solar power plants, the use of biogas energy,

the construction of eco-houses with heat and cold control, etc. Smart solutions are also associated with an increase in quality agricultural productivity. "Smart Village" is an economic unit with developed systems of science and education, which form the basis of the city's economy and provide a comfortable living environment by achieving a high environmental effect, and is being built taking into account advanced international experience. Turkish, Italian and Chinese companies are taking part in the implementation of this project. "Each "Smart Village" is created taking into account the specifics of the area, the mentality of the people, the traditions and habits of the people. In a word, in Karabakh the "Smart Village" is being created in an atmosphere inherent in Azerbaijani culture" [1, p.81].

It is known that our liberated lands are rich in renewable energy resources. Thus, the Fizuli, Jebail, Zangelan and Gubadli regions have solar energy potential, the mountainous areas of Lachin and Kelbajar have wind and geothermal energy, and the Terterchay, Bazarçay, Khyakarychay rivers and small rivers of the region have great hydropower potential. "Currently, relevant work is being carried out towards transforming Karabakh into a "green energy" zone. Preparation of the concept of a "green zone" or "green space", which will cover the use of renewable energy sources, energy efficiency, the use of environmentally friendly technologies and other issues in this region, began shortly after the glorious victory in the Patriotic War [4, p. 226].

President Ilham Aliyev noted in one of his speeches that "By the end of this year, the first solar power plant with a capacity of 240 MW should be launched. But this is only the first step. We have already signed memorandums and contracts to generate 10 GW of electricity. Thus, if half of these memorandums are implemented, this will be more than enough to provide energy to a large area in Europe. At the same time, this will allow us to save large amounts of natural gas, which we currently use to produce electricity. And this gas will also go to the international market" [9,web]. As a consequence of the above, many countries, including the USA and Australia, are showing interest in green energy in Azerbaijan. Germany alone plans to invest about \$1 billion in renewable energy sources in Azerbaijan. It should be especially noted that the prospects for the development of the alternative energy market in Azerbaijan open up opportunities for many companies with relevant experience to implement various projects, both in the field of wind energy and in solar generation, hydropower and other areas of green energy. There is no doubt that the implementation of large-scale projects in these areas in the Karabakh region will help our country become a producer and important supplier of alternative energy to Europe. As a result, we can conclude that "Azerbaijan is fully determined to restore and revive the territories liberated from occupation at the highest level and form

them as a new model of regional development in the region" [3, p. 260].

"Karabakh - Azerbaijan"!!!

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